

Comparison of Homotopy Analysis Method and Residual Power Series Method for Space Fractional Navier-Stokes Equations

Bewar Salahadeen FAREEQ¹, Mine Aylin BAYRAK^{2,*}

¹ Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Arts and Science, Izmit, Kocaeli, 41001, Turkey, ORCID: 0000-0002-0713-6387

² Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Arts and Science, Izmit, Kocaeli, 41001, Turkey, ORCID: 0000-0001-7716-3455

Article Info

Oral Presentation

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14331709

Keywords

Caputo derivative
Homotopy Analysis method
Navier-Stokes equations
Residual Power series method

Abstract

The aim of this article is to apply Homotopy Analysis (HAM) and the Residual power series method (RPSM) to space fractional Navier-Stokes equations. First, the definitions of derivatives of fractional order are expressed and the important properties of these derivatives are given. Then, using the Caputo derivative, the space fractional Navier-Stokes equation was examined and its numerical solutions were shown with tables and graphs. The results obtained reveal that the proposed method for solving fractional differential equations is an effective one.

1. Introduction

Fractional differential equations, which include fractional derivatives or fractional integrals, have attracted a lot of attention from scientists in physics, biology, and chemistry, among other disciplines. Recent researches have shown that fractional derivatives and integrals may be used to effectively simulate a wide range of phenomena in the scientific domains, including fluid mechanics, biology, physics, engineering, and other fields [1-4]. Fractional ordinary differential equations, fractional partial differential equations of significant physical relevance, and integral equations can be solved employing a range of analytical and numerical methods, with using the homotopy analysis method (HAM), analytic approximate solutions have been provided for a nonlocal initial boundary value problem in which one of the classical conditions has been replaced with an integral condition. Either initial conditions or boundary conditions can be used to achieve the series solution [5-10].

The Jordanian mathematician Omar Abu Arqub initially developed the RPSM in 2013 in order to calculate the values of the coefficients of power series solutions. RPSM is a convenient and reliable method for creating power series solutions for both linear and nonlinear problems that doesn't require discretization, linearization, or perturbation [11-13]. The Navier-Stokes equation was derived by French engineer Claude Navier as an addition to Euler's equation that took viscosity into account. Initially concerned in blood flow, Navier arrived to the viscous concepts by use of a molecular method [14-16].

There are two primary forms to describe Navier-Stokes equations. One is represented by the compressible flow

equations, where the mass and momentum conservation equations and the energy equation are related by the equations of state. This form takes into account the potential for density fluctuations brought on by variations in the flow field's temperature and pressure. The next form is known as the equations of incompressible flow. Since the liquids and gases of this kind move slowly, the fluid's density doesn't change.

In this study, our objective was to assess the performance of the Navier-Stokes equation using both the Homotopy Analysis Method (HAM) and the Residual Power Series Method (RPSM).

2. Preliminaries

Definition 1: The Mittag-Leffler function is defined as:

$$E_{\alpha}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + 1)} \quad (1)$$

A two-parameter function of the Mittag-Leffler type is defined by the series expansion

$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}, \quad \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (2)$$

Definition 2: Let $\beta > 0$ be a real number and $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ an integrable function. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of f of order β is given by the expression

$$I^{\beta} f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{\beta-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (3)$$

where Γ denotes the Gamma function

* Corresponding Author: bewar.fareeq@uod.ac

Definition 3: The space-fractional derivative of order β is defined as:

$$D_x^\beta u(x, t) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\beta)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{n-\beta-1} \frac{\partial^n u(x, \tau)}{\partial \tau^n} d\tau, & n-1 < \beta < n \\ \frac{\partial^n u(x, \tau)}{\partial x^n}, & \beta = n \in \mathbb{N} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Definition: A power series expansion of the form

$$\sum_{m=0}^{\infty} c_m (t-t_0)^{m\beta} = c_0 + c_1 (t-t_0)^\beta + c_2 (t-t_0)^{2\beta} + \dots, \quad 0 \leq n-1 < \beta < n, t \geq t_0 \quad (5)$$

is called fractional power series about $t = t_0$, where t is a variable and c_m 's are constants called the coefficients of the series.

Theorem: Suppose that f has a fractional PS representation at $t = t_0$ of the form

$$f(t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} c_m (t-t_0)^{m\beta} \quad 0 \leq n-1 < \beta < n \quad t_0 \leq t < t_0 + R \quad (6)$$

$D^{m\beta} f(t)$ are continuous on $(t_0, t_0 + R)$, $m=1,2,\dots$, then coefficients c_m of Eq. (9) are given by the formula

$$c_m = \frac{D^{m\beta} f(t_0)}{\Gamma(m\beta + 1)}, \quad m = 0,1,2, \dots, \quad (7)$$

where $D^{m\beta} = D^\beta \cdot D^\beta \dots D^\beta$ (m -times) and R is the radius of convergence.

3. Material and method

3.1. Homotopy analysis method (HAM)

Nonlinear dynamical systems are recognized to occur in a wide range of domains. Although it is quite challenging, a multitude of techniques have been developed to obtain these exact physically meaningful solutions of a partial equation. Among the most crucial techniques are Bäcklund transformation and Liao introduced a novel analytical method in 1992 called HAM based on homotopy of topology. However, Liao did not incorporate the auxiliary parameter \hbar in his doctoral dissertation; instead, he constructed one-parameter family of equations by simply applying the conventional definition of homotopy. HAM is an effective technique for resolving non-linear problems. The validity of the HAM is based on homotopy of topology, and is unaffected by the presence or absence of small parameters in the equation under consideration.

Let us consider the fractional differential equation:

$$\mathcal{N}(u(x, t)) = 0, \quad (8)$$

where \mathcal{N} is a nonlinear fractional differential operator, x and t indicate independent variables, $u(x, t)$ is an unknown function. Liao (2003) we can construct the following zeroth-order deformation:

$$(1-q)\mathcal{L}(\Phi(x, t; q) - u_0(x, t)) = q\hbar H(x, t)\mathcal{N}(\Phi(x, t; q)), \quad (9)$$

where \hbar indicates an auxiliary parameter, $H(x, t)$ is an auxiliary function, $q \in [0,1]$ is an embedding parameter, \mathcal{L} is an auxiliary linear operator and it possesses the property $\mathcal{L}(C) = 0$, $u_0(x, t) = u(0, t) + xu_x(0, t)$ is an initial guess of $u(x, t)$, $\Phi(x, t; q)$ is a function of the homotopy-parameter $q \in [0,1]$ It is remarkable that the auxiliary parameter \hbar in the homotopy analysis approach can be determined with a large deal of freedom.

If $q = 0$ and $q = 1$, it holds

$$\Phi(x, t; 0) = u_0(x, t), \quad \Phi(x, t; 1) = u(x, t) \quad (10)$$

Thus, the solution $\Phi(x, t; q)$ change from the initial guess $u_0(x, t)$ to the solution $u(x, t)$ when q increases from 0 to 1. Expanding $\Phi(x, t; 0)$ in Taylor series with respect to q , one obtain

$$\Phi(x, t; 0) = u_0(x, t) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} u_m(x, t)q^m \quad (11)$$

where

$$u_m(x, t) = \frac{\partial^m \Phi(x, t; q)}{\partial q^m} \Big|_{q=0}. \quad (12)$$

Assume that the auxiliary linear operator, the initial guess, the auxiliary parameter \hbar and the auxiliary function $H(x, t)$ are picked such that the series (9) is convergent at $q = 1$, then due to Equation (10) we have:

$$u(x, t) = u_0(x, t) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} u_m(x, t) \quad (13)$$

Now, let us define the vector

$$\vec{u}_n(x, t) = \{u_0(x, t), u_1(x, t), \dots, u_n(x, t)\}. \quad (14)$$

Differentiating Eq. (9) m times with respect to the embedding parameter q and then setting $q = 0$ and finally dividing them by $m!$ we have the so-called m th-order deformation equation

$$\mathcal{L}[u_m(x, t) - \chi_m u_{m-1}(x, t)] = \hbar H(x, t) R_m[\vec{u}_{m-1}(x, t)], \quad (15)$$

where

$$R_m[\vec{u}_{m-1}(x, t)] = \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \frac{\partial^{m-1} \mathcal{N}(\Phi(x, t; q))}{\partial q^{m-1}} \Big|_{q=0}, \quad (16)$$

and

$$\chi_m = \begin{cases} 0, & m \leq 1, \\ 1, & m > 1. \end{cases}$$

Applying the Riemann-Liouville integral operator I^β to both sides of Eq. (18) results in:

$$u_m(x, t) = \chi_m u_{m-1}(x, t) + \hbar I^\beta H(x, t) R_m[\vec{u}_{m-1}(x, t)], \quad (17)$$

It is easily to obtain u_m for $m \geq 1$ using the above recurrent formula.

Lastly, for the intent of computation, we will approximate the HAM solution (17) by the following truncated series:

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{j=0}^m u_j(x, t). \quad (18)$$

3.2. Residual Power Series Method (RPSM)

An effective analytical method called the residual power series method (RPSM), has recently been developed to handle various

forms of fractional differential equations. Additionally, this approach was successfully applied to find the solutions to a variety of fractional differential equations. A convergent series was used to provide an approximate analytical solution, which was based on the generalized Taylor series formula approach.

Consider a non-linear fractional partial differential equations of the form

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) = L(u) + N(u) \quad (19)$$

with initial condition

$$u(x, t) = f(x) \quad (20)$$

where, $L(u)$ and $N(u)$ are linear and nonlinear terms respectively. Equation(19) is expressed as the fractional power series by utilizing the RPSM concept at the initial point $t = 0$

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{f_n(x)t^{n\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + n\beta)}. \quad (21)$$

where $0 < \beta \leq 1$, $-\infty < x < \infty$, $0 \leq t < R$. Let $u_k(x, t)$ be the k^{th} truncated series of $u(x, t)$

$$u_k(x, t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{f_n(x)t^{n\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + n\beta)}. \quad (22)$$

The 0^{th} RPS approximation is,

$$u_0(x, t) = u(0, t) + xu_x(0, t) = f(x) \quad (23)$$

Eq. (19) is written as,

$$u_k(x, t) = f(x) + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{f_n(x)x^{n\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + n\beta)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \quad (24)$$

The residual function for Eq. (18) is defined as,

$$Res_u(x, t) = D_t^\beta u(x, t) - N(u) - R(u). \quad (25)$$

Therefore, the k^{th} residual function $Res_{u,k}$ is

$$Res_{u,k}(x, t) = D_t^\beta u_k(x, t) - N(u_k) - R(u_k). \quad (26)$$

If $Res u(x, t) = 0$ and $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Res_{u,k}(x, t) = Res u(x, t)$.

Consequently, $D_t^{n\beta} = 0$, as the fractional derivative of a constant is zero when utilizing the Caputo sense and the fractional derivatives $D_t^{n\beta}$ of $Res(x, t)$ and $Res_{u,k}(x, t)$ are same at $t = 0$ for each $k = 0, 1, \dots, k$ that is $D_t^{n\beta} Res(x, 0) = D_t^{n\beta} Res_k(x, t)$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, k$. $f_1(x)$, $f_2(x)$, $f_3(x)$, ..., let $k = 0, 1, \dots$, in Eq. (23) and substitute it into Eq. (24), applying fractional derivative $D_t^{(k-1)\beta}$ in both sides, $k = 1, 2, \dots$, and finally we solve

$$D_t^{(k-1)\beta} Res_{u,k}(x, 0) = 0, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, \quad (27)$$

Thus, residual power series approximate solution is derived.

4. Numerical Examples

Example 1. Let us consider the following space fractional Navier-Stokes equation:

$$u_t = D_x^{2\beta} u + \frac{1}{x} u_x + p + 2, \quad 0 < \beta \leq 1 \quad (28)$$

with initial and boundary condition

$$u(x, 0) = 1 - x^2, \quad (29)$$

$$u(0, t) = 1 + (p - 2)t, \quad (30)$$

$$u_x(0, t) = 0. \quad (31)$$

For the special case $\beta = 1$, the exact solution is

$$u(x, t) = 1 - x^2 + (p - 2)t. \quad (32)$$

Using boundary conditions, we get the form:

$$u_0(x, t) = 1 + (p - 2)t.$$

In Table 1, the exact solution and the values of absolute error for various values of β both HAM and RPSM are illustrated. Fig. 1 presents the graph of \hbar . In Figs. 2-3, the graph of exact solution, approximate solutions for various values of β both HAM and RPSM are presented, respectively. In Figs. 4-6, the 3D graph of exact solution, approximate solutions both HAM and RPSM are given, respectively. It can be concluded from Figs. 2-3 that approximate solutions tend to exact solution as α tends to 1 with the best approximation of RPSM.

Example 2. Let us consider the following space fractional navier-stokes equation:

$$u_t = D_x^{2\beta} u + \frac{1}{x} u_x + 2 - 9x, \quad 0 < \beta \leq 1 \quad (33)$$

With initial and boundary condition

$$u(x, 0) = x^3 \quad (34)$$

$$u(0, t) = 2t \quad (35)$$

$$u_x(0, t) = 0 \quad (36)$$

For the special case $\beta = 1$, the exact solution is

$$u(x, t) = x^3 + 2t. \quad (37)$$

Using boundary conditions, we get the form:

$$u_0(x, t) = 2t.$$

In Table 2, the exact solution and the values of absolute error for various values of β both HAM and RPSM are illustrated. Fig. 7 presents the graph of \hbar . In Figs. 8-9, the graph of exact solution, approximate solutions for various values of β both HAM and RPSM are presented, respectively. In Figs. 10-12, the graph of exact solution, approximate solutions both HAM and RPSM are given, respectively. It can be concluded from Figs. 8-9 that approximate solutions tend to exact solution as α tends to 1 with the best approximation of RPSM.

Example 3. Let us consider the following space fractional navier-stokes equation:

$$u_t = D_x^{2\beta} u + \frac{1}{x} u_x - u - 16x^2 \exp(-t), \quad 0 < \beta \leq 1 \quad (38)$$

With initial and boundary condition

$$u(x, 0) = x^4 \quad (39)$$

$$u(0, t) = u_x(0, t) = 0 \quad (40)$$

For the special case $\beta = 1$, the exact solution is

$$u(x, t) = x^4 \exp(-t). \quad (41)$$

Using boundary conditions, we get the form:

$$u_0(x, t) = 0.$$

In Table 3, the exact solution and the values of absolute error for various values of β both HAM and RPSM are illustrated. Fig. 13 presents the graph of \hbar . In Figs. 14-15, the graph of exact solution, approximate solutions for various values of β both HAM and RPSM are presented, respectively. In Figs. 16-18, the graph of exact solution, approximate solutions both HAM and RPSM are given, respectively. It can be concluded from Figs. 14-15 that approximate solutions tend to exact solution as α tends to 1 with the best approximation of RPSM.

Table 1. Comparison of the exact solution and approximate solutions for various values of β for Example 1.

t	x	Exact Solution	$\beta = 1$			$\beta = 0.9$			$\beta = 0.8$		
			HAM ($h = 1$)	HAM ($h = 0.5$)	RPSM	HAM ($h = 1$)	HAM ($h = 0.5$)	RPSM	HAM ($h = 1$)	HAM ($h = 0.5$)	RPSM
0.25	0.2	1.21	1.17	1.21	1.21	1.11832	1.18416	1.18416	1.03695	1.14347	1.14347
	0.4	1.09	0.93	1.09	1.09	0.79147	1.02074	1.02074	0.60415	0.92707	0.92707
	0.6	0.89	0.53	0.89	0.89	0.29867	0.77434	0.77434	0.01439	0.63220	0.63220
	0.8	0.61	-0.03	0.61	0.61	-0.34669	0.45165	0.45165	-0.70786	0.27107	0.27107
0.5	1	0.25	-0.75	0.25	0.25	-1.13594	0.05703	0.05703	-1.54794	0.14897	0.14897
	0.2	1.46	1.42	1.46	1.46	1.36832	1.43416	1.43416	1.28695	1.39347	1.39347
	0.4	1.34	1.18	1.34	1.34	1.04147	1.27074	1.27074	0.85415	1.17707	1.17707
	0.6	1.14	0.78	1.14	1.14	0.54867	1.02434	1.02434	0.26439	0.88220	0.88220
0.75	0.8	0.86	0.22	0.86	0.86	-0.09669	0.70165	0.70165	-0.45786	0.52107	0.52107
	1	0.5	-0.5	0.5	0.5	-0.88594	0.30703	0.30703	-1.29794	0.10103	0.10103
	0.2	1.71	1.67	1.71	1.71	1.61832	1.68416	1.68416	1.53695	1.64347	1.64347
	0.4	1.59	1.43	1.59	1.59	1.29147	1.52074	1.52074	1.10415	1.42707	1.42707
1	0.6	1.39	1.03	1.39	1.39	0.79867	1.27434	1.27434	0.51439	1.13220	1.13220
	0.8	1.11	0.47	1.11	1.11	0.15331	0.95165	0.95165	-0.20786	0.77107	0.77107
	1	0.75	-0.25	0.75	0.75	-0.63594	0.55703	0.55703	-1.04794	0.35103	0.35103
	0.2	1.96	1.92	1.96	1.96	1.86832	1.93416	1.93416	1.78695	1.89347	1.89347
1	0.4	1.84	1.68	1.84	1.84	1.54147	1.77074	1.77074	1.35415	1.67707	1.67707
	0.6	1.64	1.28	1.64	1.64	1.04867	1.52434	1.52434	0.76439	1.38220	1.38220
	0.8	1.36	0.72	1.36	1.36	0.40331	1.20165	1.20165	0.04214	1.02107	1.02107
	1	1	0	1	1	-0.38594	0.80703	0.80703	-0.79794	0.60103	0.60103

Figure 1. Graph of h .

Figure 2: Plot of the exact solution and the HAM solution for various values of β for Example 1.

Figure 3: Plot of the exact solution and the RPSM solution for various values of β for Example 1.

Figure 4: Exact solution graph for Example 1.

Figure 5: HAM solution graph for Example 1.

Figure 6: RPSM solution graph for Example 1.

Table 2. Comparison of the exact solution and approximate solutions for various values of β for Example 2.

t	x	Exact Solution	$\beta = 1$			$\beta = 0.9$			$\beta = 0.8$		
			HAM (h=1)	HAM (h=0.6667)	RPSM	HAM (h=1)	HAM (h=0.6667)	RPSM	HAM (h=1)	HAM (h=0.6667)	RPSM
0.25	0.2	0.508	0.512	0.508	0.508	0.52116	0.51411	0.51865	0.53687	0.52458	0.54229
	0.4	0.564	0.596	0.564	0.564	0.64738	0.59826	0.62120	0.72356	0.64905	0.72320
	0.6	0.716	0.824	0.71601	0.716	0.95868	0.80580	0.86221	1.14156	0.92773	1.09064
	0.8	1.012	1.268	1.01203	1.012	1.52644	1.18433	1.28757	1.85544	1.40367	1.67808
	1	1.5	2	1.50005	1.5	2.41727	1.77824	1.93862	2.92129	2.11428	2.51261
0.5	0.2	1.008	1.012	1.008	1.008	1.02116	1.01411	1.01865	1.03687	1.02458	1.04229
	0.4	1.064	1.096	1.064	1.064	1.14738	1.09826	1.12120	1.22356	1.14905	1.22320
	0.6	1.216	1.324	1.21601	1.216	1.45868	1.30580	1.36221	1.64156	1.42773	1.59064
	0.8	1.512	1.768	1.51203	1.512	2.02644	1.68433	1.78757	2.35544	1.90367	2.17808
	1	2	2.5	2.00005	2	2.91727	2.27824	2.43862	3.42129	2.61428	3.01261
0.75	0.2	1.508	1.512	1.508	1.508	1.52116	1.51411	1.51865	1.53687	1.52458	1.54229
	0.4	1.564	1.596	1.564	1.564	1.64738	1.59826	1.62120	1.72356	1.64905	1.72320
	0.6	1.716	1.824	1.71601	1.716	1.95868	1.80580	1.86221	2.14156	1.92773	2.09064
	0.8	2.012	2.268	2.01203	2.012	2.52644	2.18433	2.28757	2.85544	2.40367	2.67808
	1	2.5	3	2.50005	2.5	3.41727	2.77824	2.93862	3.92129	3.11428	3.51261
1	0.2	2.008	2.012	2.008	2.008	2.02116	2.01411	2.01865	2.03687	2.02458	2.04229

	0.4	2.064	2.096	2.064	2.064	2.14738	2.09826	2.12120	2.22356	2.14905	2.22320
	0.6	2.216	2.324	2.21601	2.216	2.45868	2.30580	2.36221	2.64156	2.42773	2.59064
	0.8	2.512	2.768	2.51203	2.512	3.02644	2.68433	2.78757	3.35544	2.90367	3.17808
	1	3	3.5	3.00005	3	3.91727	3.27824	3.43862	4.42129	3.61428	4.01261

Figure 7: Graph of \tilde{h} .

Figure 8: Plot of the exact solution and the HAM solution for various values of β for Example 2.

Figure 9: Plot of the exact solution and the RPSM solution for various values of β for Example 2.

Figure 10: Exact solution graph for Example 2.

Figure 11: HAM solution graph for Example 2.

Figure 12: RPSM solution graph for Example 2.

Table 3. Comparison of the exact solution and approximate solutions for various values of β for Example 3.

t	x	Exact Solution	$\beta = 1$			$\beta = 0.9$			$\beta = 0.8$		
			HAM (h=1)	HAM (h=0.75)	RPSM	HAM (h=1)	HAM (h=0.75)	RPSM	HAM (h=1)	HAM (h=0.75)	RPSM
0.25	0.2	0.00125	0.00166	0.00125	0.00125	0.00308	0.00231	0.00425	0.00567	0.00425	0.01397
	0.4	0.01994	0.02658	0.01994	0.01994	0.04296	0.03222	0.05159	0.06879	0.05159	0.12840
	0.6	0.10093	0.13458	0.10093	0.10093	0.20054	0.15041	0.22207	0.29609	0.22207	0.46994
	0.8	0.31900	0.42533	0.31900	0.31900	0.59838	0.44878	0.62555	0.83407	0.62555	1.17991
	1	0.77880	1.03840	0.77880	0.77880	1.39712	1.04784	1.39682	1.86242	1.39682	2.40969
0.5	0.2	0.00097	0.00129	0.77880	0.77880	0.00240	0.00180	0.00331	0.00442	0.00331	0.01088
	0.4	0.01553	0.02070	0.01553	0.01553	0.03346	0.02509	0.04018	0.05357	0.04018	0.10000
	0.6	0.07861	0.10481	0.07861	0.07861	0.15618	0.11714	0.17295	0.23059	0.17295	0.36599
	0.8	0.24843	0.33125	0.24843	0.24843	0.46602	0.34951	0.48718	0.64957	0.48718	0.91892
	1	0.60653	0.80871	0.60653	0.60653	1.08808	0.81606	1.08784	1.45046	1.08784	1.87667
0.75	0.2	0.00076	0.00101	0.00076	0.00076	0.00187	0.00140	0.00258	0.00344	0.00258	0.00847
	0.4	0.01209	0.01612	0.01209	0.01209	0.02606	0.01954	0.03129	0.04172	0.03129	0.07788
	0.6	0.06122	0.08162	0.06122	0.06122	0.12164	0.09123	0.13469	0.17959	0.13469	0.28503
	0.8	0.19348	0.25798	0.19348	0.19348	0.36293	0.27220	0.37942	0.50589	0.37942	0.71565
	1	0.47237	0.62982	0.47237	0.47237	0.84740	0.63555	0.84721	1.12962	0.84721	1.46155
1	0.2	0.00059	0.00078	0.00059	0.00059	0.00146	0.00109	0.00201	0.00268	0.00201	0.00660
	0.4	0.00942	0.01256	0.00942	0.00942	0.02029	0.01522	0.02437	0.03249	0.02437	0.06065
	0.6	0.04768	0.06357	0.04768	0.04768	0.09473	0.07105	0.10490	0.13986	0.10490	0.22199
	0.8	0.15068	0.20091	0.15068	0.15068	0.28265	0.21199	0.29549	0.39399	0.29549	0.55735
	1	0.36788	0.49051	0.36788	0.36788	0.65995	0.49496	0.65981	0.87975	0.65981	1.13826

Figure 13: Graph of \hat{h} .

Figure 14: Plot of the exact solution and the HAM solution for various values of β for Example 3.

Figure 15: Plot of the exact solution and the RPSM solution for various values of β for Example 3.

Figure 16: Exact solution graph for Example 23.

Figure 17: HAM solution graph for Example 3.

Figure 18: RPSM solution graph for Example 3.

5. Conclusions

In this research, Homotopy Analysis Method (HAM) and Residual Power Series Method (RPSM) are applied to the solution of the space fractional Navier-Stokes equation. It can be seen that HAM gives better results for smaller values of h within a certain range. For small values of time t , RPSM shows superior performance compared to HAM and the solutions of both methods are in close agreement with the exact solution for the given examples.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal-special permission.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

References

- [1] Bayrak M.A., Demir A., 2018. A new approach for space- time fractional partial differential equations by residual power series method. *Appl. Math. Comput.*, 336, pp. 215–230.
- [2] Demir A., Bayrak M.A., 2019. A New Approach for the Solution of Space-Time Fractional Order Heat-Like Partial Differential Equations by Residual Power Series Method. *Commun. Math. Appl.*, 10(3), pp. 585–597.
- [3] Guo B., Xueke P., Huang F., 2015. *Fractional Partial Differential Equations and Their Numerical Solutions*-World Scientific Publishing Co World Scientific Publishing Co. Pte. Ltd.,
- [4] Momani S., 2005. An explicit and numerical solutions of the fractional KdV equation. *Math. Comput. Simul.*, 70(2), pp. 110–118.
- [5] Mesloub S., Obaidat S., 2012. On the application of the homotopy analysis method for a nonlocal mixed problem with Bessel operator. *Applied Mathematics and Computation*, 219(8), pp. 3477–3485.
- [6] Rahman M.M., Murshed .M., Akhter N., 2022. A comparison of the homotopy analysis method method and the homotopy perturbation method for the korteweg-de vries (k-dv) equation. *Int. J. Sci. Eng. Res.*, 13(9), pp. 153–171.
- [7] Ragab A.A., Hemida K.M., Mohamed M.S., El Salam M.A., 2012. Solution of Time-Fractional Navier-Stokes Equation by Using Homotopy Analysis Method. 13(2), pp. 13–21.

- [8] Abbas Z.M.A., 2014. Homotopy Analysis Method for Solving System of Non-Linear Various Problem of Partial Differential Equations. *Int. Inst. Sci. Technol. Educ. E-Journals.*, 4, pp. 113–126.
- [9] Jafari H., Sayevand K., Tajadodi H., Baleanu D. 2013. Homotopy analysis method for solving Abel differential equation of fractional order. *Cent. Eur. J. Phys.*, 11(10), pp. 1523–1527.
- [10] Mohyud-Din S.T., Yildirim A., Usman M., 2011. Homotopy analysis method for fractional partial differential equations. *Complexity*, 6(1)(1), pp. 136–145.
- [11] Arqub O.A., 2013. Series Solution of Fuzzy Differential Equations under Strongly Generalized Differentiability. *J. Adv. Res. Appl. Math.*, 5(1), pp. 31–52.
- [12] Chakraverty S., Jena R.M., 2023. Residual Power Series Method Theorems and Lemma Related to RPSM Basic Idea of RPSM, pp. 129–138.
- [13] Xu F., Gao Y., Yang X., Zhang H., 2016. Construction of Fractional Power Series Solutions to Fractional Boussinesq Equations Using Residual Power Series Method. *Math. Probl. Eng.*, 2016
- [14] Ahmad R.S., 2015. An analytical solution of the fractional Navier-Stokes equation by residual power series method. Zarqa University.
- [15] Khan H., Khan Q., Kumam P., Tchier F., Ahmed S., 2022. Chaos, Solitons & Fractals : X The fractional view analysis of the Navier-Stokes equations within Caputo operator. *Chaos, Solitons Fractals X*, 8, p. 100076.
- [16] Aigner A.A., 2020. Navier-Stokes Equation, no. March 2004, pp. 1–4.